

A METHOD TO CHARACTERIZE BIAXIAL STRENGTHENING EFFECTS WITH A UNIAXIAL TEST

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ABSTRACT

Existing biaxial failure envelopes for composite laminates demonstrate conflicting material performance, such as failure envelop shapes that range from oval to diamond. This paper seeks to determine which shape represents the physical behavior of composites by using a unique uniaxial experimental and verifying it biaxial data and analytical predictions made using techniques of varying complexity. The uniaxial test consists of sets of carbon fiber/epoxy material tensile coupons composed of a QI layup. The first set aligned the 0 degree laminate direction with load application. The remaining six sets rotated the layup away from load application in 7.5 degrees increments up to 45 degrees. This approach has the potential to characterize a laminates biaxial strengthening because, when applying a fiber dominated lamina failure criteria, the strength in the test case rotated by 22.5 degrees should increase by 24 percent over the aligned case. This approach was further investigated with biaxial coupons that also varied the laminate's alignment relative to load application. Three analysis method were utilized, 1) classical laminated plate theory, 2) 3-D FEA modeling only in-plane failures, and 3) 3-D FEA modeling both in-plane and delamination failures. The misaligned specimens failed up to 27 percent lower than the aligned coupons which contradict the fiber dominated lamina failure predictions. Likewise, none of the CLPT predictions matched the uniaxial experiment; however, as the 3-D model complexity increased the predictions better correlated to the test data. The final analysis results indicate delamination was the primary cause of failure. Conversely, the biaxial data demonstrated a 22 percent strength increase, which supports the biaxial strengthening theoretical predictions, and provides evidence that the misaligned laminate uniaxial test is not an accurate characterization of the laminate's performance. The simulated predictions for the biaxial experiment also correlated well and showed that delamination was not the cause of failure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Previously published analytical and experimental research characterizing the biaxial failure envelopes for composite laminates has reported conflicting material performance. Figure 1 displays competing analytical predictions for a Quasi-Isotropic (QI) carbon fiber-epoxy resin composite

laminate, plotted over experimental results published by Welsh in 2007 [1]. One prediction using the Polynomial Invariant failure criterion, published by Christensen in 2009 [2], evaluates the material on a laminate level and demonstrates reasonable agreement with Welsh's experimental results. The other prediction, which is typical of fiber dominated lamina failure criteria, is a distinctly different shape. The diamond shaped failure envelope is caused by a maximum strain type failure criterion in the material's fiber direction. The resulting strength increase under biaxial loading is commonly referred to as biaxial strengthening, some failure criteria predict an increase up to 50 percent greater than the laminates uniaxial strength. Although Welsh's data does not support this material behavior, research published by Hinton, in 2002 [3], demonstrated good analytical comparison to biaxial failure data generated by Swenson that realized strengthening in quadrant's I and III.

This paper seeks to determine which failure envelope shape represents the materials physical behavior by using a unique uniaxial experimental approach. To accomplish this, uniaxial and biaxial experimental data is compared to various analytical predictions made using a variety of analysis techniques of varying complexity. In doing so, this work aims to further understand how various analysis techniques can be appropriately used for failure prediction.

2 TECHNICAL APPROACH

As an initial attempt to realize biaxial strengthening, seven sets of ASTM 3039 uniaxial tensile test coupons composed of the same carbon fiber/epoxy material (IM7/8552) and quasi-isotropic layup [(90/45/0/-45)_{2s}] were fabricated and tested. The first sample set aligned the 0 degree fibers with the coupons load application direction. The remaining six sets rotated the layup's 0 degree away from the load application direction in 7.5 degree increments up to 45 degrees. Due to symmetry conditions, the angle between load application and laminate fibers was greatest in the 22.5 degrees coupon set. This experiment has the potential to characterize a laminates biaxial strengthening performance because when applying the fiber dominated lamina failure criteria to this test configuration the strength in the test case rotated by 22.5 degree should increase by 24 percent over the 0 degree aligned set since it takes a greater imparted displacement, and thereby applied force, to induce the equivalent critical strain level into the fibers of the misaligned specimens compared to the aligned laminate specimens. If this hypothesis were verified, this relatively simple test could be used to prescribe a laminates biaxial performance relative to its uniaxial strength.

The next experimental phase subjected four sets of cruciforms specimens to equal biaxial tensile loading. The first set aligned the laminate with load application, and the subsequent sets rotated the laminate 7.5, 15, and 22.5 degrees. The cruciforms consisted of the same material system and QI layup as the ASTM 3039 coupons. The intent of this phase was to evaluate if the laminate performance in the uniaxial specimens was a result the coupon geometry or represented the overall laminate properties. The final aspect of the experimental plan was conducting standard material characterization tests to provide consistent, cohesive, reliable engineering constants for the analytical models.

In parallel, the failure strengths were analytically predicted and compared to the experimental results. Three analysis method were chosen for investigation, 1) classical laminated plate theory (CLPT) based analysis using Autodesk Helius Composite, 2) three-dimensional finite element analysis using Abaqus and Autodesk Helius PFA (Progressive Failure Analysis) modeling only in-plane

Figure 1: Conflicting biaxial failure envelopes

failures, and 3) three-dimensional finite element analysis of the coupon using Abaqus and Helius PFA modeling both in-plane and delamination failures.

The CLPT approach is the simplest of all of the approaches. It uses well known closed form solutions to calculate failure of a laminate based on lamina strength values, and an assumed uniform stress state that neglects any localized out-of-plane loading. Because of the simplifying assumptions and ease of use, the failure predictions for 8 different failure criteria were calculate in a matter of minutes. However, the underlying assumptions of CLPT are violated when failure evolves away from uniformity which limits the applicable scope of these calculations.

Using 3-D finite element analysis while considering only in plane failure adds a level of complexity to the simulation, adding to the set-up and computational burden, however the increased complexity usually provides insight into localized behavior and damage evolution. Modeling a specimen or structure considering only in-plane failure is often adequate if there is not large out-of-plane loading or significant edge effects. The simulations (including model set-up) conducted for this paper for in-plane failure were completed in about half a typical work day and interrogated two failure criteria.

The highest degree of complexity considered in this work involves using 3-D finite element analysis while considering both in-plane and out-of-plane failure simultaneously. In this case, the FEA model size is increased significantly due to the presence of cohesive elements between every ply, and model creation difficulty increases exponentially. Additionally, determining the input values for cohesive properties creates another level of complexity and, in this case, these values were not experimentally determined.

3 ANALYTICAL PREDICTIONS

Multiple failure criteria were analyzed using the CLPT approach including Max Stress, Max Strain, Tsai-Wu, Tsai-Hill, Hashin, Christensen (2008), Puck, and Multicontinuum Theory (MCT). The results of these analyses are shown in Figure 2. The analysis was conducted using the progressive failure capabilities offered in Autodesk Helius Composite. Upon failure, degradation factors were applied to the composite lamina stiffness as follows: E22 = 1% of the original value, G12 = 10% of the original value. The laminate was considered failed when the first fiber failure was reached.

Figure 2: CLPT failure predictions

First, one can note that all methods show symmetric behavior about the 22.5° rotation angle. Next, the analysis results can be divided into three response groups based on a changing rotation angle; a group that shows strengthening, a group that stays relatively constant, and a group that shows significant softening. Puck's and Christensen's criteria both show significant strengthening, Tsai-Wu, Tsai-Hill, Hashin, and MCT stay relatively constant, and Max Stress and Max Strain show significant weakening.

Three dimensional finite element analysis was performed using Abaqus and Autodesk Heliuss PFA. The entire specimen was analyzed using discrete layer (one element per ply) modeling technique. The Hashin and MCT failure criteria, as implemented with Heliuss PFA, were used for failure initiation prediction and the fiber and matrix constituents were degraded separately based on the failure mode predicted by the criteria. In these analyses, only in-plane, lamina level failure was considered. The results are graphed in Figure 3. First, one can observe that both results are now unsymmetric about the 22.5 rotation angle. Next, the Hashin results now generally show weakening behavior, while the MCT results oscillate about the 0° value. Also, the 0° value for each of these criteria is lower than the CLPT result, this is because the 3-D FEA model shows some stress concentrations near the grips, which initiate the failure whereas the CLPT assumes a constant stress state across the specimen.

Figure 3: 3-D FEA failure predictions for uniaxial test configuration

The final analysis method for the uniaxial tension coupons added cohesive elements to the three dimensional FEA models to simulate delamination. Cohesive properties were estimated using existing data, but were not verified for this material system. Based on the analysis results it appears that the cohesive inputs are under-predicting the behavior of the interface between plies, however it is useful to note the role that delamination plays into the results. These results are also plotted in Figure 3. A first observation of these results is that the ultimate strength of the laminate is much lower than the previous predictions. An improvement could be made by experimentally calibrating the cohesive strengths to this material system. However, the trend of the strength with respect to rotation angle is very interesting. It appears that delamination plays a major role in creating an unsymmetric response about the 22.5° rotation angle.

Similar to the method described above, the biaxial specimens were simulated using three dimensional finite element analysis and Abaqus along with Heliuss PFA. The entire specimen was

analyzed using discrete layer (one element per ply) modeling technique. In this case, the MCT failure criteria was used for failure initiation prediction and the fiber and matrix constituents were degraded separately based on the failure mode predicted by the criteria. In this analysis, only in-plane, lamina level failure was considered. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Biaxial cruciform failure prediction

The analytical predictions of the biax specimen show a fairly significant (approximately 14 percent) increase in strength from 0 to 15 degrees, then a plateau through 22.5 degrees where the strength doesn't increase. The predicted behavior is also symmetric about the 22.5 degree line. This is much different than what was predicted when applying the same analysis methods to the uniaxial tension coupon.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A three phase experimental plan was executed consisting of, 1) ASTM material characterization to generate the material constants needed to accurately model the coupons, 2) uniaxial response of a QI laminate whose alignment with the load application varied, and 3) biaxial response of a QI laminate whose alignment with the load application varied. All coupons were made from the same material batch.

Table 1: IM7/8552 engineering constants

	$S_{11,ut}$ ksi	E_{11+} Msi	$S_{22,ut}$ ksi	E_{22+} Msi	$S_{11,uc}$ ksi	E_{11-} Msi	$S_{22,uc}$ ksi	E_{22-} Msi	τ_{12} ksi	G_{12} Msi
1	484	28.4	8.0	1.25	-204	18.2	-35.9	1.28	15.5	0.69
2	463	27.3	8.5	1.25	-207	18.6	-36.4	1.30	15.6	0.67
3	479	27.7	7.7	1.30	-210	18.5	-34.7	1.26	15.7	0.66
4	470	27.4	8.1	1.30	-212	17.2	-36.7	1.31	15.6	0.71
5	469	28.5	7.7	1.26	-202	17.8	-37.2	1.25	15.7	0.66
Ave	473	27.9	8.0	1.27	-207	18.1	-36.2	1.28	15.6	0.68
max	484	28.5	8.5	1.30	-202	18.6	-34.7	1.31	15.7	0.71
min	463	27.3	7.7	1.25	-212	17.2	-37.2	1.25	15.5	0.66
stdev	8.4	0.6	0.3	0.02	4.1	0.6	0.9	0.03	0.06	0.02
COV (%)	1.8%	2.0%	4.1%	1.9%	2.0%	3.2%	2.6%	2.0%	0.4%	3.2%

Engineering constants for the subject material, 66% fiber volume fraction IM7/8552, were generated by conducting 0° and 90° ASTM D3039 tension tests, D5379 shear tests, and D6641 combined loading compression tests. Five coupons were tested to failure for each engineering constant, the results of which are summarized in Table 1.

In the second phase, the balanced and symmetric laminate ASTM D3039 tension specimen geometry was used to evaluate five coupons for each alignment angle. The results were very consistent in regards to the individual specimens' failure surfaces, shown in Figure 5, and data agreement, shown in Table 2. The ultimate strengths Coefficient of Variance (COV) for each data set was less than 3 percent, likewise the Young's Modulus and ultimate strain COV's were less than 3 and 4 percent, respectfully, for each data set. Additionally, the experimental results demonstrated an equivalent stiffness regardless of the laminate's alignment with load application, however, the misaligned specimens failed up to 27 percent lower than the aligned coupons and 19 percent lower in the 22.5 degree coupon set, which contradicts maximum fiber strain failure criteria predictions. This trend is graphed in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Uniaxial test coupon failure surfaces

Table 2: QI laminate uniaxial strength results

Spec	S _{ut} (ksi)						
	0	7.5	15	22.5	30	37.5	45
1	135.0	113.9	111.6	105.9	106.6	112.5	138.2
2	131.4	121.8	109.0	110.0	103.1	116.1	131.3
3	127.7	113.3	109.5	113.8	103.8	115.5	131.5
4	135.9	116.9	112.2	114.9	103.4	112.7	132.6
5	129.9	116.6	105.7	110.4	104.3	109.6	129.6
ave	132.0	116.5	109.6	111.0	104.2	113.3	132.6
max	135.9	121.8	112.2	114.9	106.6	116.1	138.2
min	127.7	113.3	105.7	105.9	103.1	109.6	129.6
stdev	3.4	3.4	2.6	3.5	1.4	2.6	3.3
cov	2.6%	2.9%	2.3%	3.2%	1.3%	2.3%	2.5%

Figure 6: Uniaxial failure strengths of the misaligned QI laminate

A possible explanation for this outcome is the 22.5 degree load application angle created a large shear traction on the surface lamina edges that was relieved through the interfaces in the edge region, causing early failure due to delamination. To further examine these results, similar biaxial cruciform specimens were fabricated, for the final experimental phase, to evaluate if the QI laminate's performance in the uniaxial test was an artifact of the test method, or if it represented the global performance of the laminate. Four sets of cruciform coupons were subjected to equal biaxial tensile loading at the Air Force Research Laboratory Space Vehicles Directorate's triaxial test facility shown in Figure 8 [4]. Its electromechanical test frame is capable of generating any combination of tensile or compressive stresses in the $\sigma_1:\sigma_2:\sigma_3$ stress space and can evaluate the uniaxial, biaxial, or triaxial response of composite materials. Similar to the uniaxial tests, the laminate was aligned with load application in the first set of coupons, and rotated by 7.5, 15, and 22.5 degrees in the three subsequent sets. Due to the relatively symmetric response of the uniaxial tests, biaxial experiments were not conducted for 30, 37.5, and 45 degree laminate alignments. A sample cruciform gage section (post failure) is shown in Figure 5. The specimen's square, tapered thickness gage section eradicates free edge effects while generating a consistent biaxial loading in its center. This experimental approach provides two benefits, first its tapered thickness gage section alleviates failure due to delamination, and second it will quantify the laminates true performance relative to its alignment with load application for comparison to the uniaxial test results.

Figure 7: Biaxial cruciform failure surface

Figure 8: AFRL triaxial test facility

The biaxial test data is tabulated in Table 3. The consistency of the results is in-line with the other data presented in this paper and all laminate orientation sets have a COV less than three percent. The trend line, shown in Figure 9 along with the uniaxial trend line, demonstrates a 22 percent strength increase from the in-line load application to the misaligned laminate, which supports the biaxial strengthening theoretical predictions, and indicates the misaligned uniaxial test is not an accurate characterization of the misaligned laminate’s load carrying capability.

Table 3: Biaxial test results (ksi)

Spec	0		7.5		15		22.5	
	$S_{ut,x}$	$S_{ut,y}$	$S_{ut,x}$	$S_{ut,y}$	$S_{ut,x}$	$S_{ut,y}$	$S_{ut,x}$	$S_{ut,y}$
1	83.7	83.2	85.2	85.7	94.3	95.1	105.2	104.7
2	84.2	84.2	87.6	88.4	94.0	95.3	104.6	104.1
3	87.0	86.5	89.0	90.3	91.2	91.0	102.6	100.9
ave	85.0	84.6	87.3	88.1	93.2	93.8	104.1	103.3
max	87.0	86.5	89.0	90.3	94.3	95.3	105.2	104.7
min	83.7	83.2	85.2	85.7	91.2	91.0	102.6	100.9
stdev	1.76	1.68	1.92	2.28	1.71	2.40	1.33	2.06
cov	2.1%	2.0%	2.2%	2.6%	1.8%	2.6%	1.3%	2.0%

Figure 9: Uniaxial and biaxial experimental results

5 COMPARISON OF ANALYTICAL PREDICTIONS TO EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 10 shows a comparison of the CLPT results for multiple failure criteria and the 3-D simulation of the uniaxial experiment to both the uniaxial and biaxial experimental results. All analysis result shown are for uniaxial loading only.

Figure 10: Comparison of uniaxial analytical predictions to uniaxial and biaxial experimental results

The first thing to note is that none of the CLPT predictions, regardless of failure criteria, match well with the uniaxial experiment. This is due to the fact that the failure mechanism caused non-uniform load distribution which in turn violated the CLPT assumptions. This highlights the limitations of the CLPT calculations, since the method assumes a uniform stress state and neglects any damage evolution and stress redistribution that may be caused by delamination it is unable to capture the behavior of the misaligned laminate uniaxial specimens.

Some encouraging trends are shown in the 3-D FEA, such as unsymmetric behavior, but the results do not correlate very well in general. This also supports the notion that delamination is a key contributor in the ultimate failure of the specimen and its effects are ignored in this simulation.

When 3-D FEA is coupled with delamination predictions, the trend of the results are very close to the experimental observations, however the magnitudes are not correct. This is likely due to cohesive input properties; although relevant input properties were used, they were not taken from direct experimental data. An experimental and analytical correlation exercise could be conducted to improve this, however, that was not in the scope of this project. The agreement in the trend of the results supports the discussion in the Analytical Predictions section that delamination is a significant contributor to the failure of the misaligned laminate uniaxial specimens.

Figure 11: Comparison of the biaxial experimental results to analytical predictions

Finally, a comparison of the biaxial experimental results with the 3-D Autodesk Helius PFA analytical predictions is shown in Figure 11. The experimental and simulated results have fairly good agreement across the range of load application angles. The simulation does not capture the peak at 22.5°, however, the correlation at 0°, 7.5°, and 15° are all within 5%. The simulation results at 22.5° are approximately 10% below the experimental data. Delamination was not simulated in this analysis, and the good correlation indicates that it is not a significant contributor in the failure of these specimens. Only the MCT criteria were used in this simulation, and it does not show a strengthening for the CLPT predictions. Christensen's criterion does show strengthening for a uniaxial specimen misaligned by 22.5°, so correlation could improve using that failure criteria in the biaxial model.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The data from all three phases of the experimental plan showed good consistency with low COV's typically ranging from 2 to 3 percent, which indicates the test methods produced accurate results. The misaligned laminate uniaxial test data did not demonstrate the predicted strength increase as the laminate rotated away from load application, however, analysis and the biaxial test data indicate it should have. The biaxial cruciforms realized a 22 percent strength increase over the in-line load application to the misaligned laminate, which supports the biaxial strengthening theoretical predictions, and indicates the misaligned uniaxial test is not an accurate characterization of the misaligned laminate's load carrying capability.

From an analytical perspective, different failure criteria predicted varying strength responses as the load application angle changed. The CPLT tool provides an excellent opportunity to observe how each failure criteria responds given its quick calculation speeds and ease of use, but it is limited in scope to uniform loading scenarios.

As the problem complexity increased, as in the case of the misaligned laminate uniaxial specimens, the CPLT method's inherent assumptions limited its use. Two types of 3-D FEA simulation were conducted, one without the simulation of delamination and one that included delamination simulation. Results demonstrating the correct trends were achieved using 3-D FEA simulation with delamination, but not accurate magnitudes. This highlights two items, 1) the failure behavior of the misaligned laminate uniaxial specimens is very complex, and 2) simulating such complex behavior is very difficult even on the material characterization coupon scale. For the biaxial specimens 3-D FEA

simulations without delamination provided excellent correlation to the experimental data, indicating delamination did not significantly contribute to failure.

Ultimately, the simulation work shown here highlights that there are simulation tools of varying levels of complexity available, and it is important to take care in choosing the one that is most appropriate to the problem being simulated and is capable of returning meaningful results, while minimizing computational expense.

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